

Overcoming Consumer Barriers in Green Apparel: Insights into Motivations and Challenges

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Abstract:

This article explores the multifaceted behaviour of consumers regarding sustainable fashion. It focuses on the various possibilities for environmentally friendly apparel, the factors that motivate consumers to embrace these options, and the obstacles that prevent customers from making decisions. The purpose of this study is to get an understanding of the factors that inspire consumers to select environmentally friendly clothing and to identify the primary obstacles that arise throughout the decision-making process. The most significant barriers are insufficient awareness, problems with availability, brand association, high pricing, the allure and accessibility of quick fashion, a lack of information, ugly designs, the absence of buying incentives, and worries about product quality. On the other hand, key motivators are accessibility, awareness, brand recognition, style, comfort, cost, and proficient marketing communications. When it comes to developing policies that encourage more sustainable practices, the findings of this research give valuable insights that firms, legislators, and stakeholders may utilise in the fashion sector. The fashion industry can increase the adoption of environmentally friendly clothes and play a role in contributing to a more sustainable future by addressing the constraints that consumers face and harnessing essential motivators.

Keywords: *consumer perception, ethical fashion, green apparel, green marketing, sustainable fashion, sustainable goals*

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1. Introduction

Understanding why people buy eco-fashion is essential, especially as consumers become more aware of sustainability issues. A comprehension of these incentives is the main focus of this work. Research into the reasons that drive excessive consumption still needs to be explored, which is an important subject that requires additional inquiry [1]. Although there is a sizeable client base for eco-friendly design, the market for this type of clothing is still considered a niche industry, mainly appealing to people who are ecologically concerned. Many producers, designers, and merchants struggle to align their eco-friendly products with consumers' aesthetic preferences [2]. The recycling of abandoned clothing into "upcycled" fashion, which effectively appeals to consumers who are both environmentally concerned and fashion-conscious, is pioneered by a few designers [3].

Over the past decades, there has been a growing trend to link global warming and climate change to excessive consumerism. The fashion industry is also criticised for encouraging quick clothing turnover. Fast fashion is one of the factors that has led to an increase in the amount of trash clothes left in landfills worldwide. Producing one kilogram of cotton takes around one kilogram of oil and between 7,000 and 29,000 litres of water [4]. The steady influx of new

design trends and the rapid replacement of older goods are the primary motivating factors behind customers' tendency to throw away apparel without considering these environmental implications [5]. A considerable proportion of garments are thrown away owing to production problems, despite the yearly output of garments reaching roughly 100 billion pieces [6]. Approximately 12.8 million tons of clothes are discarded in landfills across the United States each year, according to estimates provided by the Environmental Protection Agency [7]. This duration has been decreased to only weeks due to fierce rivalry and manufacturing that takes place overseas [8]. Fashion-conscious consumers used to keep their items for at least six months. Although eco-fashion and sustainable fashion aim to address this issue, more research is needed to understand the motivations behind eco-fashion purchases. It is of the utmost importance to address the factors that lead to excessive consumption, and to do so, further academic research is required [1]. Although there is an increasing number of environmentally conscious consumers, this industry remains a niche market focused on environmentally conscious ones. Most manufacturers and designers continue to strike a balance between satisfying the needs of consumers for appearance and usefulness while still being environmentally friendly [2]. On the other hand, forward-thinking designers who transform unwanted garments into fashionable, upcycled outfits have expanded their customer base to include individuals interested in social and environmental concerns and fashion trends [3].

"According to a 2023 report by GlobalData, the sustainable fashion market has grown at a CAGR of 10% over the past decade, reaching a global value of \$100 billion by 2024." The

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significant increase in eco-friendly apparel sales reinforces critical points about the growing consumer interest in sustainability. This trend underscores the fashion industry's shift towards more environmentally conscious practices and can be used to make data on sustainable fashion more accessible and memorable.

2. Literature review

Eco-friendly fashion refers to recycled, vintage, or second-hand garments manufactured with minimal toxic chemicals. The use of organic fibres in the production of this clothing is manufactured without the use of harmful bleaches and dyes [9]. Cotton, jute, hemp, and bamboo are examples of organic fibres encouraged to be used in eco-fashion [10]. These fibres have a lower impact on the environment. Another characteristic that distinguishes eco-friendly apparel is its refusal to engage in harsh or experimental practices on animals [11]. Similarly, clothing that has been rented or leased is regarded as environmentally friendly, along with things that have been recycled or antique. Concepts such as "minimalism" further assist in achieving sustainable objectives [12].

Recent developments in consumer preferences demonstrate that variables related to convenience and habitual behaviour frequently take precedence over environmental concerns when making purchase decisions [10]. Consumers are always on the lookout for fashion things that are not only fashionable but also visually appealing [11]. Even though eco-fashion is better for the environment, it needs help attracting customers who are concerned about their sense of style. Style, social status, and financial considerations frequently motivate consumer fashion decisions [12]. Ecological concerns have a minor impact on these choices. Customers concentrate on energy usage and recycled materials when discussing eco-friendliness, even though they are aware of the issues associated with sustainability. According to [13], more than people's environmental concerns are needed to dissuade them from purchasing fast fashion. The findings of [14] indicate that customers emphasise fashion and cost more than environmentally friendly design.

Furthermore, the researchers discovered that consumers' understanding of sustainability concerns had minimal influence on their purchasing behaviour [15]. Eco-fashion is still considered a niche business, and its acceptability as a mainstream industry is still in its early stages. Eco-fashion is even though there is a rising interest in fast fashion's social and environmental implications [12].

2.1 Barriers to eco-fashion purchase

According to the research, its premium price tag is the most significant barrier to eco-fashion purchase [16]. Even though customers know why eco-fashion is beneficial, the cost remains a significant barrier. To encourage customers to change their buying habits, the fashion industry must make environmentally conscious solutions more financially

accessible [17]. The pricing rivalry that eco-fashion firm's face comes from fast fashion giants, which have economies of scale that eco-fashion does not have [14]. However, eco-fashion brands need help to compete with rapid fashion giants. Brands such as Zara, Topshop, and H&M encourage disposable clothing practices, undermining sustainable consumption [18]. This tendency results from the high cost of eco-fashion and the quantity of low-priced fast fashion. All these factors contribute to the rising trend of "throwaway fashion." The hesitation of customers to purchase eco-fashion is not just a result of price [19].

Not only is there a restricted supply of environmentally friendly clothing, but the eco-fashion business is also relatively tiny, which is another big hurdle. Despite being seen as eco-friendly, purchasing second-hand clothing faces challenges due to personal and cultural factors. [16, 20]. Consumers often hesitate to buy pre-owned items due to concerns about appearance and potential stigma. The authors discovered that although many customers are willing to purchase used clothing, only a small percentage do so, highlighting cultural obstacles. Several contextual issues, like a lack of experience with thrift stores and the amount of time necessary for shopping, are also factors that discourage individuals from frequenting these thrift stores. Most customers prefer new clothing over previously owned clothing, partly because they want to give the impression that they have a better social standing through their clothes [21].

Consumers need help understanding the environmental effects of the apparel they purchase because the supply chain lacks transparency [22]. Researchers argue that understanding manufacturing locations, materials, and care practices is essential [9]. The fashion industry has been hesitant to share this information, which has resulted in customers needing more knowledge to make purchase decisions [17]. Other studies imply that natural fibres could impact the environment more than synthetic ones, even though natural fibres are almost always advertised as more sustainable [23].

Customers frequently need to see operational advantages in purchasing eco-fashion [16]. Customers continue to emphasise receiving attractive, high-quality, and comfortable clothing; eco-brands are required to fulfil these criteria [22]. Another complicating factor is the perception that wearing eco-friendly apparel is a sign of weakness [24]. Research has found that consumers' behaviours frequently do not correspond with their beliefs and values, even though they have a pro-sustainability mindset [12, 22].

2.2 Motivational factors

Understanding the aspects that impact consumers' decisions about their clothes is crucial since they evaluate fashionable clothing based on various characteristics. To fulfil the requirements of their customers, eco-fashion firms need to modify both their goods and their business operations. It is found that inexpensive products are frequently abandoned

without feeling guilty and that price plays a crucial role in how long customers keep garments. Consumers are prepared to spend a higher price on high-quality, environmentally friendly clothing [13]. However, they have less interest in purchasing goods previously owned or mended by themselves. Consumers are willing to spend more on ecologically friendly apparel [19]. Eco-fashion becomes more appealing when it enhances social status. Based on the findings, attitudes towards environmentally friendly apparel are highly influenced by benevolence, status, perceived consumer efficacy, and personal pleasure, which propose that customers only purchase eco-clothing if the advantages exceed the work and associated expenses [21].

Many individuals are motivated to purchase used clothes because they would rather not spend time searching for environmentally friendly fashion; used clothing is more convenient. Even eco-fashion doubters are drawn to well-designed eco-fabrics of excellent quality. The desire to show one's unique style is a significant incentive for purchasing fashion. Individuals are aware of the positive effects that organic cotton has on the environment. As a result, they choose to buy clothing manufactured from organic cotton to show their support for organic farmers [14].

Instead of being seen as a compromise between style and duty, eco-consciousness should be considered an upgrade. The use of eco-labelling and excellent communication to emphasise the environmental advantages of their products is recommended by [24] for eco-fashion firms to establish credibility. Green marketing and retail displays that highlight the beneficial environmental impact of eco-friendly clothing can also be effective ways to increase sales. Thrift businesses should guarantee that things are well-cleaned and reframe thrift shopping as a contemporary and environmentally responsible habit [16]. Addressing the social stigma and hygienic problems connected with used apparel is essential. Some thrift stores call their inventory vintage to highlight the one-of-a-kind qualities and historical significance of the objects they sell. Although environmental concerns are a driving force behind the purchasing decisions of some customers, notably college students who are typically more environmentally concerned, there is still a need for a more widespread appeal [20].

The use of celebrity endorsements can assist in expanding the market for environmentally friendly clothing. Getting celebrities to promote social and environmental problems through the use of "cause-related marketing" has shown to be successful. In a survey conducted, it was revealed that customers are prepared to pay a higher price for items obtained from businesses that emphasise sustainability [25]. Celebrity endorsements are a potent instrument for marketing environmentally friendly apparel since celebrities have a significant impact on the choices that consumers make [26].

3. Gap analysis

The current body of literature extensively studies the obstacles and motives influencing eco-fashion. Only a few studies have been conducted on this topic, especially about sustainable, quick, and ethical clothes. A significant portion of the research that is now accessible is restricted to a particular geographic area. It frequently employs a generalised sample, which is mainly comprised of female fashion college students. Compared to other demographics, young college students are more willing to engage in environmentally conscious activity [20]. Regarding the opinions of working and non-working professionals outside the fashion sector, this study focuses on people from the moderate to high-income categories. The purpose of this study is to fill the research gaps that have been identified. By taking this technique, we want to understand their standpoints toward used clothing. When people's financial resources are limited, they purchase used apparel, a frequent trend [20, 21].

4. Methodology

This study aims to determine the variables driving and impeding the adoption of eco-fashion among consumers from a consumer perspective. The research uses a qualitative methodology to investigate the "thoughts and feelings" of the participants [27, 28]. This study aims to understand the extent to which eco-fashion is being adopted, why some customers choose not to embrace it, and what would inspire them to do so. To acquire in-depth story data, questionnaires are less successful than open-ended and thorough interviews [29]. The data was acquired through semi-structured interviews that lasted 25 to 30 minutes. Because of the potential for bias resulting from the participant's knowledge of the fashion business, none were associated with the fashion industry. The sample includes 30 male and female respondents who visited green apparel stores in Ludhiana and Jalandhar, Punjab. A purposive sampling technique was administered to collect the data. This research employs 18 male and 12 female participants between the 25 to 35 age group with PG and higher qualifications of middle-income group profile. According to the research that has been conducted, one of the most significant obstacles presented by eco-fashion is its high price [16, 18 & 30]. This study included a varied sample of participants to discover new non-cost-related barriers and motivators. Our goal is to provide a thorough knowledge of the main hurdles and incentives that influence eco-fashion consumption by including persons who are working and individuals who are not working, as well as men and women.

Research questions

1. What are the barriers that prevent consumers from adopting green apparel?
2. What are the motivational factors that affect the purchase of green apparel?

5. Results

5.1 Barriers to eco-fashion adoption

5.1.1 Awareness of the Eco-Wear Movement

Most respondents needed a thorough comprehension of eco-fashion, as was discovered through the analysis of the interview transcripts. The phrases "clothing made without synthetic fibres," "garments from cottage industries," and "affordable and economical fashion" were all used by some of the participants to characterise those who participated. Because cotton is thought to be innocuous to the environment, some people feel that cotton clothing is environmentally benign. Although most participants were aware of the connection between eco-friendliness and the environment, they needed help comprehending how their decisions about their clothing affect the environment. Those who had some familiarity with ecologically friendly items used phrases such as "recycled," "environmentally friendly," "non-toxic," and "organic." According to the survey findings, there is a considerable knowledge and comprehension gap around eco-fashion among the respondents, with many indicating a need for further information. The sheer amount of information was overwhelming and unpleasant for some participants, who better understood the subject matter. These participants also mentioned that excessive technical jargon made their purchasing experience more challenging.

5.1.2 The absence of eco-friendly clothing selections

Participants expressed a strong desire for more accessible eco-friendly clothing options. They reported a lack of environmentally friendly clothing tags at retail outlets but indicated a willingness to purchase such items if they were more readily available. Customers have high expectations that their favourite brands and prominent retail shops will offer and provide knowledge about these things. This demand for accessible eco-fashion could potentially influence retailers' stocking decisions and increase the availability of eco-friendly clothing in the market.

5.1.3 The Difference between Expensive Eco-Fashion and Affordable Fast Fashion

Many participants held the misconception that sustainable apparel was expensive and only targeted people with higher incomes. This belief led them to assume that young customers do not have the financial means to purchase environmentally friendly clothing. However, this view was not entirely accurate. While some eco-fashion items may be pricier, affordable options are also available. The prevalence of commercials from well-known companies and the availability of reasonably priced apparel alternatives throughout the year further reinforced this misconception. Dispelling this myth could broaden the appeal of eco-friendly clothing.

5.1.4 Styles that are not appealing and the quality that is perceived

Some participants thought eco-friendly clothing lacked flair

and excitement and associated it with a harsh and unpleasant image. When it came to eco-fashion, many had preconceived conceptions, associating it with clothing of inferior quality and items purchased from flea markets. Even though some people bought organic food, they felt they needed to be more encouraged to purchase environmentally friendly clothing.

5.2 Motivational factors

According to the information gathered, the most critical aspects that motivate people to purchase environmentally friendly clothes are the availability of sustainable apparel, knowledge of the issue, and endorsements from celebrities and businesses. Brand reputation, product style, and price strongly influence participants' decisions. They stated they would be more likely to purchase eco-fashion if presented with persuasive marketing messaging.

5.2.1 Brands, styles, and the aesthetic appeal of the product

Many participants were primarily motivated by exclusivity, design, and style concepts. Simple marketing strategies can boost the appeal of eco-friendly clothing, with attractive designs from popular brands playing a crucial role in purchase decisions. According to the research, providing only environmentally friendly clothes is not enough; it is essential to emphasise fashion and aesthetic appeal.

5.2.2 Availability and Cost-Effectiveness of the Product

The respondents thought eco-fashion would substantially influence their purchase decisions if available in mainstream retailers and from the brands they favoured. Many individuals emphasised affordability, indicating they would be more likely to buy eco-fashion if reasonably priced.

5.2.3 Marketing and Communication Strategies

Celebrity and brand endorsements' impact on consumers' behaviour is a significant factor in the success of eco-fashion promotion. If celebrities or businesses that stressed the beneficial influence of eco-friendly clothing on the environment were to promote it, most respondents said they would be more likely to purchase eco-friendly apparel. To increase their adoption rate, eco-fashion companies must improve their marketing techniques to increase customer knowledge and educate them about their products.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

The study effectively fills the identified research gap by focusing on understanding the barriers and motivational factors that influence the adoption of eco-fashion among working and non-working professionals who are not part of the fashion industry. This demographic, particularly those from moderate to high-income categories, has been underrepresented in previous research, primarily focusing on young female college students involved in fashion studies. This study broadens the scope of understanding by including a diverse sample that spans various occupational statuses and genders. It provides a more comprehensive view of consumer behaviour towards eco-fashion.

Despite a growing awareness of environmental issues, eco-fashion remains a niche market primarily due to significant barriers such as high costs, limited availability, and a perceived lack of style and quality. Many consumers, particularly those outside the fashion industry, have misconceptions about eco-friendly clothing, often associating it with inferior quality and higher prices. The lack of accessible and appealing eco-fashion options further exacerbates these issues, hindering widespread adoption. Key findings related to this research are awareness gaps, accessibility, affordability, perceived lack of style, and marketing influence.

There is a pressing need for educational campaigns that inform consumers about the benefits of eco-fashion and debunk myths related to its cost and style. Brands and retailers should focus on transparency in the supply chain, emphasising the environmental impact of eco-friendly products. To increase adoption, eco-fashion brands must focus on making their products more accessible and affordable. This can be achieved through partnerships with mainstream retailers and developing more cost-effective production methods. Eco-fashion brands need to prioritise style and quality in their offerings. By ensuring that eco-friendly clothing meets consumer expectations for fashion and aesthetic appeal, brands can overcome the perception that sustainable fashion is less desirable. Marketing strategies should leverage the influence of celebrities and social media to promote eco-fashion. Cause-related

marketing that highlights the environmental benefits of eco-friendly clothing can effectively increase consumer interest and adoption.

Overall, the research adds to the existing body of knowledge by filling a specific demographic gap. It provides practical implications for how the eco-fashion industry can overcome current barriers and leverage motivational factors to expand its market reach. By addressing these fundamental barriers and focusing on the motivational factors identified in this study, eco-fashion brands can broaden their appeal and encourage more sustainable consumer behaviour. This approach will help reduce the fashion industry's environmental impact and make eco-fashion a mainstream choice for consumers.

7. Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

This study's findings should be interpreted considering several inherent limitations. The study focused solely on the issues identified as most significant by Indian consumers during qualitative discussions, with partial support from the existing empirical literature. Since this study was exploratory, future research is needed to validate these findings. Conducting studies with a nationally representative sample, encompassing diverse geographic and demographic factors, and including additional questions would enhance the validity of the results.

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